

BEHAVIOR AS A FUNCTION OF ECOLOGICALLY VALID EXPERIMENT

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Research problem

The present Quality of Experience (QoE) subjective testing is done by asking users about the quality after watching the video sequence. The most popular scale is Absolute Category Rating (ACR), where people rate the quality from 1 (Bad) to 5 (Excellent). However, this approach is unnatural because in real life, people take action to improve video quality rather than passively rate the degraded video. The need to conduct behavior-oriented tests led to adapting psychometric methods to the QoE subjective tests. Fitting the psychometric function allows the individual differences in quality perceiving to be noticed. The additional approach will be creating the mean psychometric function for all participants.

Planned experiments

Getting information about perceived quality without asking about quality

1. The participant chooses any movie on Netflix
2. The experimenters qualified for the experiment by conducting vision and color-blindness tests
3. The participant signs the consent and provides information needed for payment for the participation
4. The participant watches the video with an experiment instruction in which they are encouraged to push the button when the quality is unsatisfactory. As a result, the quality of the movie will be increased to the best possible
5. The main part of the experiment is controlled by the Chrome plugin, which decreases video quality monotonically until the participant presses the button or the quality is the lowest available on the server
6. The participant can react to the quality of the movie while watching the movie
7. To press a button, which is located close to the TV screen, a participant has to stand up
8. Pressing the button stops the movie for up to two seconds
9. After the movie, the participant fills out the online questionnaire regarding their experience

Preliminary results

The presented results were gained from 42 people, of which twenty-seven identified as female, thirteen as male, and two didn't want to specify. The average age of the participant was 39.2. From this group, three people did not react to the quality degradation:

- One person (male, 20) was used to such a bad quality
- One elderly person (female, 64) complained of back pain which makes getting up and pushing the button impossible
- One elderly person (female, 64) claimed she didn't understand the instructions.

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Research questions

- Q1: How can psychometric analytical methods be adopted for video quality experiments?
- Q2: What is the internal validity of a new subjective experiment focusing on behavior?
- Q3: How can behavior be derived as a function of video quality?
- Q4: How is the behavior in the lab comparable to the behavior at home?
- Q5: How is JND compared to the proposed ecologically valid experiment?

Read more

The whole idea of my PhD thesis and its scientific background is broadly described in <https://doi.org/10.1145/3573381.3597235>.

Differences in perceiving quality

The preliminary results analysis shows that the psychometric functions' shape for different participants differs. The psychometric functions belong to the family of the sigmoid function, so reversing the standard VMAF value (where 100 is the best quality and 0 is the worst quality) was necessary. Due to readability, I present the small subgroup of 5 participants in this picture. We can see that the people differ in terms of the **threshold** when the quality is unacceptable for them and their **precision** when they press the button. **In classical subjective experiments, we cannot see such differences.**

Contact

If you have any questions or suggestions or want to collaborate, do not hesitate to contact me via e-mail: wanat@agh.edu.pl.

